

BUSINESS ETHICS, ENVIRONMENTAL JUSTICE, AND THE PATH TO SUSTAINABILITY. INTERDISCIPLINARY REFLECTIONS ACROSS ANTHROPOLOGY AND ECONOMICS

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Abstract. *‘Sustainability’ has become a widespread buzzword (mantra) in almost all spheres of human activity, including business. Several meanings have been attributed to this term. Essentially this term denotes social responsibility, environmental justice and ethical business practice. Business ethics refers not only to fair treatment of directly involved human subjects (employees, suppliers, intermediaries, customers etc.) but also to fairness in all business operations considering their impact on society and environment. It is about fairness in the use/share of natural resources considering all contemporary human groups and all living and sentient creatures as well as forthcoming generations who face degradation and scarcity that the adults leave behind after having relentlessly pursued material economic growth. Business organizations as active economic actors are increasingly solicited to reduce their negative externalities and conduct their affairs in an ethical and just manner. Therefore, the quest for sustainability is basically about ethical business practice and environmental justice. This little paper intends to share some interdisciplinary reflections based on the observation of business ethics and environmental justice in different cultural contexts; it also aims to indicate new directions for entrepreneurship-led sustainable development.*

Keywords: *Business, Development, Environment, Ethics, Justice, Sustainability.*

Global institutionalization of ‘sustainability’

Sustainability has become firmly institutionalized as a widely popular concept in policy debate and public discourse. Scholars have noticed diversity in the use of the term ‘sustainability’, multiple meanings attributed to the concept and, consequently, divergent interpretations and outcomes (Yamada, Kanoi, Koh, Lim & Dove, 2022). In 1987, United Nations’ World Commission on Environment and Development defined ‘sustainable development’ as the “development that meets the needs of the present generation of humans without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs” (UN-WECD, 1987) in its first report. Subsequently, in 1992, the United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (also known as ‘Earth Summit’), took place in Rio de Janeiro (Brazil) where the heads of state and government of almost all member-countries of the United Nations participated to discuss about economic development with environmental justice for all sections of humanity. Following the 1992 Earth Summit, the UN member states adopted a comprehensive plan of action (known as ‘Agenda 21’) to build a global partnership for sustainable development.

The 1992 Earth Summit played an influential role in affirming some key-principles of environmental justice (e.g. the ‘polluter-pays’ principle). A key achievement of the 1992 Earth Summit was the establishment of United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), an international memorandum undersigned by more than 160 governments with the clear aim to contrast negative environmental externalities of economic activities by reducing the

emissions in the atmosphere which are supposed to alter planet's climate, ecological equilibrium and biodiversity. In 2000, UN member states unanimously adopted the 'Millennium Declaration' that led to the elaboration of the 'Millennium Development Goals' (MDGs) which culminated in the Johannesburg Declaration (2002) on Sustainable Development. In 2015, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) adopted the Agenda for Sustainable Development with seventeen 'sustainable development goals' (SDGs) to be achieved by 2030 A.D. UNGA delegated the task to a high-level political forum - Division for Sustainable Development Goals (DSDG) - to serve as the central platform for the follow-up and review of the progress in all seventeen sustainable development goals.

In recent years, scientific research projects and social initiatives in the fields of sustainability, climate risks and environmental security have continued to develop all over the world. The civic sector (non-governmental organizations, cultural associations etc.) and the educational institutions have been prominent participants in this process. Local/regional administrations, national parliaments and governments of many countries have steadily increased policy directives and normative complexity in pursuit of sustainability. Policy initiatives have been undertaken for ecological transition, renewable energy expansion, net-zero carbon emission and circular industrial cycles. The mainstream media organizations, both public and corporate, have served as the amplifying soundboxes of sustainability debate. Consumers and citizens of all walks of life have been influenced by the 'sustainability' challenge. Private business organizations too are concerned with sustainability. In the last two decades, almost all medium-to-large business organizations have been publishing their own sustainability reports. Some business organizations have been trying to align their sustainability efforts with efficiency and cost-cutting management. Some others have used their environmental improvement announcements with marketing and corporate communication which, sometimes, have been proved to be misleading self-aggrandizement (e.g. the recent case of Adidas, a large German corporation producing and selling sportswear).

The imperative of sustainability stems from a deep concern for Earth's ecosystem, for equity and fairness in sharing natural resources and in shouldering environmental burdens and, above all, in ensuring justice for all human groups and their future generations as well as for all living and sentient beings and their offsprings. Business organizations as active economic actors are increasingly solicited to ensure environmental justice by reducing their negative externalities, by conducting their affairs in an ethical manner and by compensating in some way for the unavoidable negative externalities generated in the business process. After all, the foundation of business relationships rests upon pillars of trust, honesty, and reliability. Ethical business management that upholds environmental justice helps to build trust.

Business Ethics

A study conducted on a sample of 350 private Italian business organizations with more than 100 years of history and the in-depth study of 16 of these ultra-centenary business entities, to investigate the phenomenon of corporate longevity, highlighted a close link between business ethics and the ability of the company to last over time (Giarretta, 2004). The reconstruction of the profile of companies that were over a hundred years old, and the identification of their vitality-longevity offers interesting insights into the relationship between ethics in business management and the ability of the company to continue profitably and survive longer. The study found that out of a total of almost 5 million companies operating in Italy at the beginning of the 21st century,

companies that were over a century old represented a very small fraction, about 0.015%. Over the years and decades, many corporate organizations, even those of great financial success, have already become extinct. While some organizations have survived longer despite not having had spectacular financial success but only moderate profitability; presumably, due to their reputation for trustworthiness and reliability. The short life-span of many business organizations, despite the great financial successes achieved in their historical period, leads us to ask whether the lack of ethical values could represent one of the causes of the non-longevity of most companies.

The famous economist and Nobel Prize winner of 1976, Prof. Milton Friedman of the USA, once argued that the ethical imperative for business organizations was to maximize profit and nothing else. However, before Friedman's assertion, there were business organizations that had already set a different vision, highlighting the feasibility of a business model that considered the needs of society and the environment. An important example is that of Olivetti S.p.A.. Immediately after the World War II, Mr. Adriano Olivetti, world famous Italian engineer, industrial entrepreneur and politician, managed to create a new and unique business experience in a period in which two political ideologies, capitalism and communism, embodied by two super-powers (USA and USSR), faced each other as opposites. Mr. Olivetti believed that it was not only possible but also morally urgent to create a balance between justice, solidarity and profit (Olivetti, 1937, 1952, 1960). Olivetti's organization included an idea of collective happiness that generated efficiency (Mornese, 2005). Olivetti workers lived in better conditions than in all other large Italian factories. They received higher salaries and subsidized housing. There were nurseries, cultural and recreational facilities near the factory that respected the beauty of the landscape and integrity of the environment. Olivetti decreased the hours of work and increased the salaries and fringe benefits for the workers. In late 1950s and early 1960s, Olivetti workers were the best paid of all in the manufacturing industry in Italy, and Olivetti workers showed the highest productivity. Adriano Olivetti's attempt at utopia was translated into practice as actions of an enlightened business leader (Kent, 1957). Adriano Olivetti's entrepreneurship is considered one of the world's brightest examples of responsible leadership, ethical practice and business success. In addition to Olivetti, many successful entrepreneurs have challenged Friedman's assertion and provided examples of ethical business practices geared towards sustainability, including some large Japanese corporations that have displayed excellence in business ethics.

In line with Prof. Friedman's statement, the majority of business scholars and entrepreneurs once considered the term 'business ethics' as an oxymoron (Collins, 1994). However, today, business ethics is an established field, recognized for its role in promoting moral principles and sustainable practices in industrial and commercial organizations beyond the compliance of legal obligations (Holland and Albrecht, 2013; Swanson and Fisher, 2011). It is important to distinguish the legal obligations from the ethical responsibilities (Crane *et al.*, 2019). Legal obligations exist to prevent disorder and harm to society, and not to create virtuous behaviour. Ethics is about moral responsibility. The law is binding and uniformly applied in society, while moral responsibility is voluntarily assumed by individual units (persons, firms, associations etc.) of society in their own ways. Legal obligations are compulsory requirement in any society. The ethical responsibilities refer to voluntary actions expected by society and cherished by the public at large (Carroll, 2016). It is equally important to understand how and why the moral responsibility is perceived differently by different stakeholders (García-Rosell, 2019). So, to understand the societal and public expectations and the reasons behind them, ethical theories become essential (Mäkinen *et al.*, 2024).

Business ethics is about the application of moral principles to a business context and about

the moral responsibility assumed by business units. It is based on the analysis of the reasons behind moral/immoral behavior. It offers norms and codes of conduct to evaluate and justify the morality of business practices and decision-making (Crane *et al.*, 2019). Undeniably, integrating ethics into organizational practices can make strategic planning and decision-making more complex and challenging. Technological advancement and digitalization of society have added new challenges, especially in areas like the use of data diffusion, sophisticated automation, robotics and artificial intelligence (Bartneck *et al.*, 2021).

Three main theoretical approaches prevail in the field of business ethics: the teleological approach that emphasizes utility and impact, the deontological approach that focuses on rights and duties in a specific sector/profession, and the virtue approach that highlights morality (Jones *et al.*, 2005). The multiplicity of approaches challenges the assumption of a singular universal ethics, suggesting instead that there are different perspectives on ethics. Numerous ethical theories have been proposed as the foundation of business ethics, and this often causes considerable confusion. Many theories are often proposed without serious discussion of their philosophical foundations and their historical and cultural backgrounds. Some theories focus on duties or obligations, others on responsibility for consequences, virtues or moral feelings. Furthermore, some theories focus on universal principles, while others take the singularity of each situation as the focal point. These differences cannot be satisfactorily addressed through ethical pluralism, in which all theories are accepted, without falling into moral relativism. Ethical pragmatism, which accepts an ethical theory only based on its practice and success, is also questionable. Finally, there is the problem of integrating ethics into business theory, which is often extrinsic to the economic function of a business organization (Melé, 2023).

In addition to its role in evaluating actions and helping to understand different interpretations of moral responsibility by business organizations, ethics can also serve as a means of promoting critical reflexivity (introspective awareness/mindfulness) within the organizations; this means acknowledging ourselves and our actions in relation to others (Cunliffe, 2008). Engaging in ethical deliberation can trigger critical reflexivity, encouraging individuals to question assumptions and make sense of the existence and responsibilities of business in society. Critical introspection and reflexivity are needed to develop more ethical ways of organizing and relating to each other (Cunliffe, 2004; García-Rosell, 2019). Ethics as a means for introspective reflexivity and mindfulness provides an opportunity for questioning the established norms, mainstream narratives in the business world and society, and future perspectives.

Business ethics is a well-established discipline, but there remains room for further development. Conventionally, the focus has been on rights, duties and virtues; however, incorporating such humanistic aspects such as relationships, empathy and care have yet among humans, other living creatures and Nature, could fill these gaps (Jones *et al.*, 2005; Böhm *et al.*, 2022). Although business ethics has drawn inspiration primarily from Western traditions, it is important to explore also the non-Western traditions such as Vedic-Sanatana (so-called "Hindu"), Taoism, Buddhism, Confucianism, shamanism and tribal traditions, to enrich knowledge and broaden perspectives (Berger & Herstein, 2014; Chan, 2008). Western business ethics has mainly remained anthropocentric, neglecting the ethical considerations of animals, other non-human living beings and Nature (Böhm *et al.*, 2022; Kortetmäki *et al.*, 2023). By studying the non-anthropocentric ethical perspectives that emphasize caring relationships among humans, all other living and sentient creatures and their natural environments, we may gain new insights into the notion of responsibility within business ethics. This new horizon of study leads us to the core

issues of environmental ethics and environmental justice.

Environmental ethics

The planetary-scale environmental challenges faced by modern humans in the 21st century seem to have never been experienced before. Until the last century, environmental challenges were limited to local natural hazards and occasional disasters (e.g. earthquakes, droughts, floods, landslides, forest fires, etc.). Until the early 20th century, the human population was small (circa 1.6 billion), most human habitats were relatively small and less complex, consumption and ecological impact were limited. For the vast majority, resource-use and consumption were confined to the local context of a predominantly subsistence economy based on primary sector (agriculture, livestock, forestry, fishery...). Human activities required less energy and generated much less waste, which was mostly bio-degradable, regulated by environmental feed-back loops (decomposition and recycling in nature) and dissipated within a narrow material flow circuit. This is no longer the case. The global human population now exceeds 8 billion. The process of satisfying the basic needs of global humanity requires more and more energy, resources and space. Since 2005, more than half of the world's population has settled in urban areas and has become a mass consumer of industrial products and services. The development of transportation and the expansion of global trade and supply chains have caused mass consumerism even in remote rural areas. The overall volume of resource use, energy use and material consumption, both per capita and absolute-cumulative, is increasingly high. The volume of waste is larger, growing further and faster. Almost all industrial and municipal waste is non-biodegradable and is linked to the pollution of soil, water and air, space consumption, bad smells and aesthetic degradation of landscapes. The ever-increasing volume and intensity of energy use and material flow on the earth's surface are threatening the integrity of human habitats, natural ecosystems and vital resources that support life. Therefore, environmental ethics that promotes self-restraint in human actions towards Nature has become a strategic imperative for sustainability and survival.

Elements of environmental ethics and sustainable livelihood were strongly present in the primitive (tribal) cultural contexts and ancient civilizations of East Asia. Those ideas are expressed in terms quite different from modern ones. The idea of 'sustainability', in terms of human self-restraint, eco-compatible livelihoods and respectful relationship with the rest of the natural environment, is found abundantly in the ancient texts of East Asian traditions: Vedic-Sanatana (commonly known as "Hinduism") and its off-shoots Buddhism and Jainism, Taoism, Confucianism, Shintoism as well as in other non-scriptural magico-religious traditions such as shamanism. The essential teachings of these traditions state that all beings, things and forces of Nature are interconnected and permeated by a common divine essence (Callicott, 1997; Baidur, 2015; Bernard, 2004; de Silva, 2013; Grim, 2001; Kaza, 2018; Mitra, 2019; Selin, 2003).

Similar ideas are found in the indigenous primitive cultures of the Americas, Africa, Oceania, the Arctic regions and other remote corners of the world (Calicott, 1997; Wenz, 1996). East Asian and tribal environmental ideas are rooted in their religious beliefs regarding the sacredness (holiness) of Nature, articulated through myths and rituals, and implemented through strict observance of behavioral codes and taboos (Turner, 2005). The phenomena/elements of Nature such as sky, sun, moon, stars, light, fire, wind, clouds, rain, snow, glaciers, rivers, lakes, mountains, trees, rocks, animals etc. are worshipped as the deities who preside over cosmic and biotic functions, i.e. cosmos-centric *Weltanschauung* articulated through bio-cosmic symbolism. Cosmos-centric *Weltanschauung* affirms that all human beings, along with all other living and

sentient creatures, are nodes in a cosmic-biotic mega-web, organically connected and interacting with each other and with the rest of the universe. Bio-cosmic symbolism that articulates such ideas does highlight humanity's awe, fear and respect for Nature. The cosmos-centric *Weltanschauung* and bio-cosmic symbolism emphasize on the sacred and spiritual essence of Nature and prescribe a strict observance of environmental norms (and taboos), and thus induce human self-control in interactions with the natural environment. All this has historically prevented an exploitative attitude towards other living creatures and the natural environment. This, in turn, has ensured stable and environment-friendly livelihoods and commercial activities, i.e. sustainability *ante litteram*.

By the beginning of 20th century, the environmental ethics based on sacral/spiritual view of Nature (cosmos-centric *Weltanschauung*) expressed through bio-cosmic symbolism was severely weakened in East Asia, Africa and other parts of the tribal world due to foreign invasions, colonial subjugation, and by organized missionary activities to convert native communities to monotheistic religions such as Christianity and Islam which have distinct theocentric, and not cosmos-centric, doctrine. Later, modernization played a big role in making traditional and tribal environmental ethics redundant all over the world. In the non-Western world, modernization has been basically Westernization that was carried out through European colonial rules first and, later in post-colonial period, through the establishment of nation-state mechanism and urban-centered, growth-obsessed economic development model. The transition to Western-inspired urban-centered growth-oriented economic development model has caused environmental degradation in many developing countries, making their shift from “another world” to “third world” irreversible. This transition from “another world” to “third world” in tribal and traditional non-Western societies is a combined result of direct Western influences, local population growth, rapid modernization and, above all, demise of indigenous spiritual traditions which constituted the primary source of values, norms and practices regarding the environment (Nasr, 1974). In most tribal and traditional societies of the contemporary non-Western world (the so-called “third world”) the sacredness of Nature and cosmocentrism have been replaced by a modern anthropocentric perspective originating in the Western world.

In the Western world, the most important historical source of conventional attitudes toward the natural environment is the Christian religion, which has spread and prevailed in Europe for nearly two millennia. Christianity, like Judaism and Islam, is a monotheistic theocentric tradition that holds belief in a divinely ordained human separation from Nature and in human supremacy (and dominion) over other living creatures and the natural environment (White Jr., 1967). In all monotheistic traditions – Judaism, Christianity and Islam – the theocentric idea is the central pillar of doctrine. God is considered the supreme patron, responsible for the creation and sustenance of Nature. Monotheistic traditions articulate paternalistic symbolism such as “Father”, “Lord”, “Master of the Universe”, “King of Heaven” and so on. Nature is viewed as something created and nurtured by a supernatural, unique, omnipotent and omniscient supreme being (i.e. God) that is above and beyond the manifest reality of Nature; and humanity is seen at the helm of all other beings and things as God's chosen deputy/delegate, created by God in His image to use and administer the Nature. This doctrine contains not only theocentric but also anthropocentric ideas. However, monotheistic traditions do promote respect for the natural environment as the work of God, urging humans to behave as responsible masters of the Earth to safeguard God's creation (Wenz, 1996).

Another important historical source of Western environmental ethics is the Greco-Roman (Hellenic) heritage prevailed in the Mediterranean basin before the Judaic, Christian and Islamic

influences. The ancient Greek thinking made a lasting impact on ancient Romans and, consequently, on European perspective. Polytheistic-pantheistic beliefs in Hellenic culture were not very different from the traditional Asian and primitive beliefs. But unlike the Asians and primitives, the ancient Greeks had a predominantly anthropocentric worldview. Humans were considered to be of superior value to the rest of living creatures and other elements of Nature, because only the human being was believed to possess reason or logical mind (God is pure reason, according to Aristotle). Following the ancient Greeks, the ancient Romans also believed that only humans possessed reason and that animals lacked it, so humanity owed them nothing (Wenz, 1996).

Alongside the classical Greco-Roman heritage, there existed many indigenous European cultures (Etruscan, Iberian, Celtic, Germanic, Norse, Baltic, Slavonic etc.). which were polytheistic in character and articulated their beliefs through bio-cosmic symbolism. In due course of time, they were converted to Christianity and got mixed up with the residual elements of Greco-Roman traditions contained in Christianity. The indigenous European traditions and their influence in shaping Western attitude to Nature should not be overlooked. Many elements of European rural folk traditions are clear expressions of some persistent undercurrents of the pre-Hellenic and pre-Christian legacies that have survived up to our times in a great variety of localized folklore. Major Christian traditions, the Roman Catholic and the Orthodox-Byzantine, have absorbed many polytheistic and Nature-worshipping elements that were once integral parts of pre-Christian (i.e., “pagan”) heritage.

The contemporary Western attitude towards Nature is partly the result of a fusion of the cultural elements from Greco-Roman, Judeo-Christian and indigenous pre-Hellenic and pre-Christian (pagan) traditions. But the most decisive role in shaping Western attitude to Nature has been played by sciences that developed in the early modern period in Europe. The ‘scientific revolution’ began towards the end of the Renaissance around the late 17th century, and continued through 18th and 19th centuries, influencing the cultural movement known as the Enlightenment (the ‘era of reason/logic’) which paved the way for modernity. Modern era developments in mathematics, physics, astronomy, biology (including human anatomy) and chemistry radically transformed the Western view of Nature.

In the modern period, the anthropocentric view of Nature and the utilitarian-exploitative attitude towards natural environment and other living creatures replaced the theocentric belief about Nature as God’s creation. Modern sciences surpassed (and ridiculed) Christian doctrine. Scientific discoveries and technological inventions helped to re-organize European institutions and economy, and enabled Europe's colonial expansion, industrialization, international trade and encounters with non-Western contexts where the Western impact triggered massive social changes thorough religious conversions, modernization, industrialization, urbanization and mass consumerism. However, in recent decades, new scientific disclosures about environmental degradation and risks (particularly the risks related to climate change) have played a great role in arousing serious doubts among Westerners about their conventional anthropocentric view of Nature and about the predatory-utilitarian attitude to natural environment. To a lesser extent, the impact of non-Western cultures, particularly those of East Asia, may have played some role in contemporary critical re-thinking on anthropocentrism. The current debate on sustainability reflects not only a critical re-thinking of traditional monotheistic beliefs and modern anthropocentric worldview but also serious doubts about science and technology as ultimate solutions to fix Earth’s and humanity’s problems. In our times, the Western world has proved to

be the most influential cultural context in shaping international institutions and global public opinion. The contemporary sustainability debate is a good example. Originated in the West, it quickly became a multifaceted global debate about ecological crisis, climate uncertainties, equity, justice, mankind's place in Nature, the role of science and technology, and human destiny.

Environmental justice

In the late 1980s, “environmental justice movement” emerged as a civic campaign in the USA. The movement began with the public exposure of disparities in sharing healthy and clean space and of unfairness and injustice in shouldering the burden of environmental degradation, pollution and public health risks - all to the disadvantage of low-income sections of society and minority communities (Bullard, 1993). Prior to that movement, sporadic local protests used to take place against invasive development, environmental pollution and hazardous waste dumpsites in the proximity of disadvantaged (low-income, minority) communities. But those protests were isolated, and protesting communities were not coordinated with other concerned communities in similar situations elsewhere. Growing public concern over the ecological crisis, media attention and environmentalism's forays into the political arena made the difference. The question of equity/justice in sharing natural resources and shouldering environmental burdens became an important political issue in the United States. With the establishment of ‘Environmental Equity Working Group’, within the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) of USA's federal government environmental justice became an institutional concern in the USA in the late 1990s. Since then, the issue of environmental justice has spread far beyond the USA. Now, it is an important component of the global sustainability debate (Bjork-James, Checker & Edelman, 2022).

In 2014, a groundbreaking act of the New Zealand parliament granted legal personality to a natural landscape what was once known as Te Urewera National Park. The New Zealand's parliamentary act created the legal entity of Te Urewera, made up of what used to be a nationally protected area, and established a board of trustees composed by the exponents of native inhabitants, the Tūhoe people (a Maori tribe), to represent Te Urewera as unique *juridic persona* and act on its behalf. Three years later, the “Te Awa Tupua (Whanganui River Claims Settlement) Act 2017” granted the same *juridic persona* status to the Whanganui River basin in New Zealand. Those legal acts were intended to deliver environmental justice for the native (indigenous) community and their local habitat. New Zealand's legal acts have affirmed that ‘environmental justice’ means recognizing that a community's habitat, identity, culture, traditional governance, spirituality and way of life are all inextricably linked to each other and embedded in a specific landscape which must be managed through traditional ecological knowledge, rules and practices of native indigenous communities such as Māori's *Kaitiakitanga*.

Environmental justice is not merely about equity and fairness in sharing the environmental resources and shouldering responsibilities among all sections of society. It is also about protecting the bio-cultural rights of communities and their habitats. ‘Bio-cultural right’ is an emerging concept in the debate around environmental ethics and human rights. This concept affirms the connection between indigenous communities and their habitats through the official recognition of inalienable ownership and perpetual stewardship of native communities over their habitats. This is markedly different from the idea of individual or corporate, commodifiable, tradable and alienable ‘ownership’ of the conventional land property market economy (Bavikatte & Bennett, 2015). The ‘biocultural right’ theory is based on historical recognition that indigenous societies

have been successful in preserving natural landscapes and biodiversity through their spiritual traditions, cultural conventions, socio-economic organization and community regulation. The indigenous populations have historically proved the ethical merit and scientific worth of their traditional holistic relationship with their surrounding natural environment. They have shown that to sustain human ecosystems it is necessary to restrain predatory-utilitarian approach to Nature and to balance (harmonize) the community's resource-use for human bio-physical needs and the environment's capacity of regeneration and self-replenishment.

There are an estimated 476 million indigenous peoples worldwide who, according to the World Bank, constitute the largest group within the world population suffering from poverty. Although the indigenous peoples make up less than 6 percent of the global population, they live in/around and manage at least 38 million sq.km of land across 87 countries which represents more than 25% of the world's land surface and intersects with circa 40% of all terrestrial protected areas with biodiversity-rich natural landscapes such as marshes, grasslands and, above all, the forests (Garnett *et al.*, 2018). Scientific studies on existing original (primeval) forest-covered lands on Earth have determined that at least 36% of world's intact forest landscapes are within various indigenous peoples' habitats and that the loss rates of intactness (integrity) of forest-covered lands have been considerably lower on indigenous peoples' habitats compared to other forest-covered lands including the formally protected areas and national parks without indigenous community presence (Fa, Watson, Leiper, Potapov *et al.*, 2020). The overlap between intact forest landscapes and indigenous peoples' habitats indicates the historical role of indigenous peoples not merely as careful and efficient users of forest resources for their livelihoods but also as irreplaceable knowledgeable custodians of the forests (Watson *et al.*, 2018).

Indigenous communities are custodians of vast areas of the world's nature reserves. Their traditional lifestyles are environment-friendly and helpful to protect biodiversity. In recent years, the positive role of indigenous communities has gained respectful attention. Indigenous communities live on and manage more than half of the world's lands but have legal ownership of only around 10% of their ancestral territories which contain some of the intact reserves of biodiversity. Their loss of control over their original habitats has been a combined consequence of encroachment from outside, modern urban-centered economic development model and public policy failures to provide environmental justice. The indigenous areas of natural reserves and biodiversity are vital to the people who live near them and manage them. They are also vital to the planet we all share. Protecting indigenous bio-cultural rights, reducing conflicts on indigenous lands and promoting the integral human development of indigenous communities, would make a significant contribution to environmental protection and well-being of all, including the communities living far from the indigenous lands.

Environmental justice comprises both the specific 'protective' justice based on the bio-cultural rights of communities and the general 'distributive' justice based on the idea of human rights and equity valid for all. It is about the inclusive participation and fair share of all in the use of natural resources and, at the same time, equity and fairness in the share of environmental burdens among all sections of society in all nations (Lehtinen, 2009). In both concepts of environmental justice - 'protective' and 'distributive' – there is basically a deep concern for the future generations. It is about making natural resources equally accessible to all contemporary human groups and environmental safety for all human groups and their forthcoming generations. Environmental justice comprises inter-generational justice (Barry, 1997, Pirni & Corvino, 2019). That means, ensuring fairness *vis-à-vis* the children and the future generations who will face the

harsh environmental and economic realities that adults of present and past generations are leaving behind after relentlessly pursuing material economic growth. We may add that the concept of inter-generational justice should not be understood as confined only to the future generations of humans but to all living and sentient creatures and their offsprings. Concern for the future generations is something humanity in general is supposed to have because the people in the future are considered as those who shall carry on with projects that are important for the present generation (de-Shalit, 1995). The potential for preserving natural resources and maintaining environmental safety for all depends on each generation playing properly its part in restraining resource-use and consumption, upkeeping the natural resources and safeguarding the environment to hand over an intact ecosystem to next generation (Barry, 1997).

Quality of context and place-brand strategy

Business organizations cannot change the world to make the planet sustainable. Because every business organization, large or small, has its natural limits of scope, resources and capabilities. But they can (and should) do their part within their limits, especially in their territory for the benefit of the native community and future generations. They can march towards sustainability through ethical practices and environmental justice in their local context where the native community deserves to receive the highest consideration. It is important to note that for business organizations ‘sustainability’ essentially means profitable continuity (staying in business without losses), not necessarily continuous growth in the volume of trade or infinite expansion in the market, as we have seen from the over a century-old companies in Italy (Giaretta, 2004).

Business continuity and pursuit of sustainability are ensured by obtaining moral legitimacy from the native community in avoiding disruption and degradation of existing resources - human, tangible and intangible (collaborators, know-how, brand prestige) – and by adding value to those resources. Therefore, in pursuing sustainability, business organizations must improve not only the quality of their products/services and the “green-ness” (eco-compatibility) of their production processes, but also the quality of the entire business ecosystem that includes all collaborators, stakeholders, participants in the value chain and their vital operating context, i.e. the local community of the territory. In other words, business organizations must act ethically, focus on justice not only within their business ecosystem, but also in their immediate surroundings, in their locality (Sapelli, 2007).

The vast majority of private companies, especially non-financial ones, in Italy and elsewhere, are characterized by their rootedness in the local socio-economic context, i.e. easy identification and proximity of the entrepreneur, interpersonal interactions and human relations, flexibility in adapting to changes. These localistic attributes facilitate business organizations’ ethical practices and environmental justice. They also facilitate the necessary consonance between the mission of the business organization, its governance, social responsibility and sustainability in the broadest sense, at the local level. Local models of sustainable practices may have application in other territorial contexts as well. In other words, we need virtuous examples of local action for sustainability in order to think globally. The road to sustainability passes through localism and not through globalism.

The basic idea of pragmatic sustainability for business organizations is to focus on the quality of their local vital and operational context, as much as on the quality of products and services. Entrepreneurs’ local civic activism, beyond pure economic functions, for the quality of their local context, has proven to be successful in promoting inter-firm cooperation and positive

cooperation with public institutions and other civic entities. Such cooperative activism of the entrepreneurs makes it easier to obtain moral legitimacy and social consensus for business. Workforce productivity and workers' loyalty are also likely to benefit from the efforts for quality of context, as exemplified by the case of Olivetti of Italy in 1950s-1960s. Even before achieving expected tangible results, which takes some time, the efforts themselves help to promote broader social cooperation and to project a distinct place brand. Once generated and promoted, the place-brand provides a competitive advantage to all local business actors (Pant, 2005). Place-branding strategy is based on shared values and measurable (and enforceable) social and environmental standards in the territory where business organizations are rooted. It can help to maintain and develop local resources, develop trade in the place, diversify local business activities, attract new investments, protect local cultural heritage, safeguard the environment, beautify landscapes and develop tourism. Even without large gains in trade and tourism, place branding efforts can certainly mobilize local resources and public opinion towards sustainability. Engaging in sustainability through quality of context and place-branding is a win/win strategy.

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